

1 **Greb1l functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Greb1l
9 as a lineage commitment factor or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem cells of the
10 human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Sanna-Cherchi, S., Khan, K., Westland, R., Krithivasan, P., Fievet, L., Rasouly, H.M., Ionita-Laza,
13 I., Capone, V.P., Fasel, D.A., Kiryluk, K. and Kamalakaran, S., 2017. Exome-wide association study
14 identifies GREB1L mutations in congenital kidney malformations. The American Journal of Human
15 Genetics, 101(5), pp.789-802.